

Entries were sown on 10 Apr and transplanted on 10 May, at 13- × 13-cm spacing, 10 hills/row, 2 rows/variety, with three replications.

In late May, all plots were infested with 50 first-instar larvae/ replication. Deadhearts were observed 1 mo after infestation.

Resistance to SB significantly differed between indica and japonica varieties. Indica varieties were more susceptible than japonicas. Of 31 japonica varieties, 79122 and Wu Fan-keng were

moderately resistant, 21 varieties were tolerant, and 8 were moderately susceptible. All 16 indica varieties were moderately susceptible or susceptible. Differences in resistance between conventional varieties and hybrids were not significant.

At 40 d after infestation, average larvae survival, body length, and head width were 21%, 11.62 mm, and 0.94 mm, respectively, in japonicas and 45.34%, 13.52 mm, and 1.3 mm, respectively, in indicas. Lower larvae

survival and shorter bodies are common characteristics on resistant varieties.

The diameter of the air cavity in the leaf sheath in moderately resistant 79122 (0.78 mm) was significantly smaller than that in susceptible Shanyou 63 (1.607 mm). The larger air cavity possibly favored larvae survival.

Amount of soluble sugar in the plant was 2.2-2.9% in moderately resistant varieties, and 3.83-4.83% in susceptible varieties. □

Resistance of rice germplasm to whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) in Changsha, China

Jiang Jian-yun, Peng Zhao-pu, Lei Hui-zhi, and Liu Gui-qiu, Plant Protection Institute, Hunan Academy of Agricultural Sciences, Changsha 410125, China

The WBPH *Sogatella furcifera* population on hybrid rice plants is

usually higher than it is on conventional varieties. To find a source of WBPH resistance for hybrid rice breeding, we conducted seedbox screening tests of 1,777 rice accessions in the greenhouse 1986-88.

Pregerminated seeds were sown in 12-cm rows in 50- × 30- × 10-cm seedboxes. TN1 and N22 were the susceptible and resistant checks. At the 3- to 4-leaf stage, each seedling was infested with seven second- to third-

instar nymphs by distributing insects uniformly on the seedbox. Plant damage was scored when susceptible check seedlings were about 90% dead.

Of 218 accessions showing resistance, 41 were resistant to both WBPH and BPH (see table). These lines and varieties can be used in breeding. The IR varieties that have also been identified as restorer lines for hybrid rice breeding will be used in that program. □

Lines and varieties resistant to WBPH and BPH in Changsha, China.

Molecular distillation of rice plants resistant and susceptible to whitebacked planthopper (WBPH)

G. Liu, Agricultural and Environmental Department (AED), University of Newcastle upon Tyne; P. Caballero, Cereal Chemistry Department, IRRI; R. C. Saxena, Entomology Department, IRRI; B. O. Juliano, Cereal Chemistry Department, IRRI; and R. M. Wilkins, AED, University of Newcastle upon Tyne, Newcastle upon Tyne NE1 7RU, UK

Attractants in susceptible rice plants and repellents in resistant plants play an important role in an insect's selection of host and establishment. We evaluated volatiles in molecular distillate extracts from WBPH-resistant Rathu Heenati and susceptible TN1 rice plants, using gas chromatography (GC).

Leaves and leaf sheaths of 7-wk-old plants were cut into 5-cm-long pieces and 100 g placed in a 500-ml glass

container, with 3 replications/variety. The container was connected to one end of a 10-cm-long U tube. The other end was connected to a glass thimble, to collect distillate. A high vacuum valve was connected 5 cm above the thimble.

The sample container was immersed into a Dewar flask containing dry ice (acetone) for 20 min. The system was connected to a high vacuum line and air evacuated until the pressure inside the container reached 10⁻³ mm Hg. Then the high vacuum valve was closed, the Dewar flask transferred to the extract collector, and the apparatus left to equilibrate at room temperature for 24 h.

GC analysis was performed on a Varian 3700 GC equipped with a wide bore 60 m × 0.75 mm SPB-1 column. N₂ was the carrier gas, at a flow rate of 3 ml/min. Injector and detector temperatures were set at 170 °C and heated to 250 °C, respectively. Oven temperature was programmed to increase from 50 °C for 2 min to

Line or variety	Scale ^a	
	WBPH	BPH
IR27280-39-2-2-3-2	0	1
IR29692-131-2-1-3	0	3
IR19661-3-2-2-3-1	0	3
IR21231-117-2-2	1	3
IR32420-130-1-3	1	3
IR28210-68-4-1-3-1	1	3
IR28251-85-1-2-3	1	3
IR25891-19-1-2	1	3
IR14497-15-2	1	3
IR19126-42-1	1	3
IR27208-102-3	1	3
IR28138-43-3-1-3-2	1	3
IR19672-195-2-2	1	3
IR21931-78-2-2	1	3
IR21817-50-2	1	3
IR18348-36-3-3	3	1
IR27300-124-2	3	1
IR24609-4-2-3-1	3	1
IR13525-118-3-2-2-2	3	1
IR19661-150-1-2-3-2	3	3
IR10781-75-3-2-2	3	1
IR13149-19-1	3	1
IR31802-56-4-3-3	3	3
IR31805-20-1-3-3	3	3
IR17494-32-1-1-3-2	3	3
Wnachyukuo	3	3
Bhusarisali Paddy	3	3
Fu 26-23	1	3
Pei hua Xuan-4	3	1

^a Standard evaluation system for rice.